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COMPARISON OF TECHNIQUES FOR DETECTION OF FAILURE ROLLING ELEMENT BEARINGS

Pavle Stepanić¹, Željko Đurović², Aleksa Krošnjar³, Aleksandra Pavasović⁴

Summary: *This paper presents advanced techniques for the detection of bearing failures based on vibration signals. Capability of detection and diagnosis of some effective techniques are discussed and compared on the basis experimental results. In particular, we analyzed the ID3 data mining technique, detection using statistical pattern recognition and application of hidden Markov model (HMM). Comparing the experimental results showed that the highest accuracy of detection techniques has been realized using HMM, and for determining the type of bearing damage easier to use a statistical approach to pattern recognition. It is shown that the presence of faults can be detected on-line monitoring of the probability of trained HMM for the correct bearing, which is determined by feature extraction from vibration signals. In addition, the application of HMM can be extended to consider problems of prognosis and prediction of bearing condition, which gives as an output time to failure.*

Key words: *failure detection, data mining, statistical pattern recognition, hidden Markov model, condition based maintenance*

1. INTRODUCTION

Most modern techniques for the detection of bearing failures is based on the analysis of vibration signals collected from the bearing housings. The common goal of all techniques is to detect the presence and type of failure at an early stage and to monitor its development in order to assess the remaining life of a system and choose the appropriate maintenance plan. Monitoring and predicting of the condition industrial systems and processes at running are activities whose importance in recent years great, as based upon the concept of preventive maintenance. Timely knowledge of a defect allows the user to correct the problem occurred during a regular repair in order to avoid additional, unplanned and often very costly delay because of sudden failure. The basic elements necessary for successful diagnosis, prognosis, and condition based maintenance (CBM) are shown in figure 1.

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Fig. 1 The basic elements condition based maintenance

The sensors are mounted on bearings that are monitored that gives the vibration signals. Then the feature extraction is to convert the signal of vibration in some type of parametric representation suitable for further analysis. Diagnostics is engaged in fault detection, isolation and identification of them when it happens. Detection of fault has a task to indicate that if something is wrong in the observed system, task of fault isolation is that find the defective component in the system while identification should determine the nature of errors which is detected. In the block for prediction is based on prognostic models and algorithms estimated the remaining lifetime of the observed bearings.

Condition based maintenance is generally limited to the failure diagnosis performance than the remaining life assessment. Diagnosis of failure is one of the most important phases in the CBM system. As a first step in diagnosis is to determine whether the error is present or not, and therefore this paper will present and compare three different methods for detection of bearing failures. Detection of rolling element bearing faults actually represents the problem of pattern recognition and classification. The following section will briefly discuss these methods and then focus more on implementation techniques and the results obtained in this study. For detailed descriptions of the techniques recommended listed references.

2. METHODS

2.1 Decision Tree

Decision tree is one of data mining techniques, and basically represents a classifier that shows all the possible outcomes of a process. The paths that lead to these outcomes are in the form of tree structure. The nodes that separate the different classes of branching based on if-then conditions. Algorithms to build trees are recursively embedded in the decision tree partitioning the training set of data successively more complete subsets. Partitioning criteria determine characteristic differences between decision trees, which are created different algorithms. ID3 algorithm uses entropy as an indicator and from initial training set partitioning it made less subset [1]. Features with the highest information gain are selected for the branch nodes based on information theory. Construction of decision tree very much depends on how the features of the training sample selected.

2.2 Statistical Pattern Recognition

The main goal of pattern recognition is to decide which category the observed pattern belongs. One of the ways in which the pattern recognition can be performed is that based on the series of patterns estimated conditional probability density functions, but such a procedure involves a very large amount of data and is associated with a number of numerical problems. Therefore, it is often applied classification methods are not optimal in any sense, but they are very simple. Commonly used parametric methods are linear and quadratic classifier [2]. In this paper we design a quadratic classifier based on the desired output.

2.3 Hidden Markov Models

HMM consists of two stochastic processes. The first process is a Markov chain with finite number state, while another process for the given state generates a series of observations. The word "hidden" means that the HMM states are not directly observable. Since the sequence of states, as the basic stochastic process is not observed, it can only be estimate through another set of stochastic processes that generate sequences of observations. Thus defined model is the basis for the description of a number of different problems. From the point of view of modeling the vibration signals from rolling element bearings, HMM can be viewed as a combination of two stochastic processes. These are the hidden Markov chains which are temporary variability of vibration signals in the hidden state sequence and observable process that explains the spectral characteristics of vibration signals. So, despite the fact that in every discrete time instant t system is in state q_t , it every step emits a visible symbol, which in general can be a continuous function (e.g. spectrum). HMM can be described by the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} X_{k+1} &= AX_k + V_{k+1}, \\ Y_k &= CX_k + W_k, \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where X_k denote hidden process, Y_k denote observation process, V_k and W_k are terms for noise, and A and C are parameters.

In general HMM is represented by triplet A, B and π , i.e. in compact notation $\lambda = (A, B, \pi)$, where the matrix A is the probability distribution of transition states, matrix B is the probability distribution of occurrence of certain symbols in certain states, and π is the initial distribution of state [3]. The problem of training HMM is a subject of adaptation (or re-estimation) model parameters $\lambda = (A, B, \pi)$ in an effort to learn and coding the characteristics of observational sequences that enable the model can continue to identify similar observation sequences. Optimization of parameters can be done Baum-Welch's iterative algorithm [3], which in this paper and used.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Experimental data were collected from the station for testing rolling element bearings. For the purposes of research and comparison of the above techniques, in this paper we used vibration signals obtained from accelerometer mounted horizontally on the bearing housing. Data were collected for the two states of bearings: normal (without defects) and defective (with some type defect). The activity preceding

classification is the determination of which measuring quantities will in the best possible way characterize the pattern that needs to be classified. For the first two methods (ID3 and quadratic classifier), extracted by 9 parameters in the time domain and 9 parameters in the frequency domain for a total of 18-dimensional feature vector, characterizing each of the tested bearings [2,4]. For HMM failure detection feature extraction from vibration signals was performed using Linear Predictive (LP) modeling for the model of 10th order.

3.1 ID3 Decision Tree

ID3 uses information gain as a measure of selection between features. In order to decrease computational complexity of algorithm for classification, dimension reduction was performed in 18-dimensional feature vectors in the new 6-dimensional space of features. The reduction of dimensions was based on KL transformation [4]. The process of discretization of continuous features in the ID3 algorithm is actually a process of selecting optimal threshold [1]. The classification was performed in two classes: defective and healthy (i.e. functional) rolling element bearings. Figure 2 shows the decision tree for the detection of bearing condition using ID3 algorithm. To test the classifier used is the "leaving-one-out" method which is estimated classification accuracy of 95.41%.

Fig. 2 ID3 decision tree

3.2 Quadratic Classifier

Quadratic classifier is designed using the desired output method. For the application and control of quadratic classifiers previously performed dimension reduction of the 18-dimensional feature vectors into two-dimensional space of features. Representation of patterns in two-dimensional space allows visualization of random vectors and easily calculate the parameters of quadratic classifiers. Dimension reduction was carried by using the criterion based on scatter measure [2]. Figure 3 shows the position of two-dimensional vectors that characterize the analyzed bearings and projected quadratic classifier. Testing the classifier, "leaving-one-out" method was obtained classification accuracy of 98.98%. In Figure 3 shows the obviously separability between defective and functional bearings. In addition, within the class of defective bearings noticeable clustering around the characteristic centers which might indicate to a particular type of bearing damaged. This is primarily result of intelligent dimension reduction based on scattering matrices which takes account of class separability.

Fig. 3 Quadratic classifier ('o' - defective bearings, 'x' - functional bearings)

3.3 HMM Fault Detection

For detecting presence of faults is enough to train one HMM for functional rolling element bearings. Sequences of observations to train HMM is obtained by dividing the vibration signal of length one second division in ten equal segments. For each of these segments (length 0.1 s) the autocorrelation method of LP coefficients are calculated for a model of order 10th. Accordingly, observational sequence consists of 10 observations, i.e., $O = O_1 O_2 O_3 \dots O_{10}$ where each of the observations O_t a 10-dimensional vector of features extracted from the LP model. Based on training observations for defective and healthy bearings codebook is generated using K-means algorithm [3]. Codebook size is $M = 128$ and on its basis will be carried out vector quantization (i.e. discretization) of continuous feature vectors. A structure model of HMM was chosen left-to-right model with three states and discrete observation symbols. Calculate the probability of resulting in a estimate to what extent a sequence corresponding to the adopted model in forward-backward procedure [3]. If the probability above a predefined threshold, then in bearing is not present defect, otherwise the bearing is faulty. One way to select an appropriate threshold is the minimum value of probability calculated for training observation sequences from normal bearings:

$$thresh = \min_{\forall \text{ normal } O} [P(O|\lambda)] \quad (2)$$

In Figure 4 a) shows the iterative step in the training of HMM and the corresponding logarithm of probability at each step. Figure 4 b) shows the logarithms of probability of vibration signals for functional bearings and bearings with defects, obtained for the HMM of functional bearings. As the figure shows bearing faults are detected with accuracy 100%. Probability of functional bearing is separated by a clearly defined threshold out of probability bearings with defect. On-line monitoring of probability HMM for functional bearings indicates ability to forecasting the condition of bearing. Developing fault in the bearing will be reflected as an unexpected change in probability, i.e. a decrease in the probability. Over time, as failure progresses, the probability of HMM for a functional bearings has a downward trend. When the bearings closer to end of useful life, the probability decreases rapidly, which indicates serious damage.

Fig. 4 a) HMM training curve b) Probabilities of normal and defective bearings

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper compares some of the modern techniques for the detection of bearing failures from vibration signals based on experimental results. Classifier based on the ID3 decision tree is clear and easy to understand. Good characteristic of this classifier is a short period of training. Estimated accuracy of detection bearing faults is 95.41%. One of the disadvantages of training phase, which can lead to less accuracy of detection is over-fitting.

Quadratic classifier is easy to use and has a high accuracy of fault detection 98.98%. This is primarily result of intelligent dimension reduction based on scattering matrices which takes account of class separability. As a result of this reduction of dimension is a clustering of damaged bearings pattern around specific centers, which can be used to determine the fault type.

Detection of bearing failures using discrete HMM of vibration signals showed classification accuracy of 100%. Time training of HMM is longer than the previous two techniques and algorithm used in training do not guarantee reaching a global maximum criterion function. Monitoring probability of HMM for functional bearings can be predicted his condition in the future and estimate the remaining useful life.

Acknowledgments

This work was created within the research project "Development of the devices for pilots training and dynamic flight simulation of modern combat aircraft: 3 DoF centrifuge and 4 DoF spatial disorientation trainer" that is supported by the Ministry of Science and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia.

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